

Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System Using IoT

Mr. D.Murugesan
Department of ECE
SRM Valliammai Engineering College
Tamil Nadu, India

Nithish Karan. J
Department of ECE
SRM Valliammai Engineering College
Tamil Nadu, India

Pradeepan. K
Department of ECE
SRM Valliammai Engineering College
Tamil Nadu, India

Prasanth G
Department of ECE
SRM Valliammai Engineering College
Tamil Nadu, India

Ragunathan M
Department of ECE
SRM Valliammai Engineering College
Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract—The IoT-based Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System is intended to offer real-time tracking of soldiers' vital signs and positions, providing improved safety, situational awareness, and quick emergency response during military operations. This system uses an Arduino Uno as the controller, combining multiple sensors like MAX30100 (heart rate and SpO₂ sensor), DS18B20 (body temperature sensor), and MQ-135 (gas sensor) to monitor the soldier's health condition continuously. The GPS Neo-6M module is employed for accurate location tracking, whereas the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module supports wireless data transmission to a cloud-based system without interruptions through the Blynk app for real-time remote monitoring by command centres. In case of unusual health conditions, exposure to toxic gases, or emergencies, the system can provide immediate alerts for prompt help. Compared to conventional GSM-based monitoring, this IoT-supported system provides quicker data transmission, enhanced accuracy, and enhanced energy efficiency. By combining smart health monitoring, GPS tracking, and IoT communication, this system offers an all-inclusive and effective solution for military use, guaranteeing improved soldier safety and operational effectiveness on the battlefield.

Keywords— Soldier safety, Wi-Fi Module, Heartbeat data, Temperature condition, Emergency, location tracking.

I. INTRODUCTION

As we are aware, enemy warfare plays a crucial role in the security matter of any state. National security primarily depends on the army (land), navy (sea), and air force (air). The central role is being played by the soldiers of the military. There are some considerations as to the security of those troopers. The future soldiers are sure to be technologically more advanced in each and every situation like war or any covert operation. Across the whole world, many analysis platforms are currently being organized, such as the United States' Future Force Warrior (FFW) and also the United Kingdom's Future Infantry Soldier Technology (FIST) and they plan to develop modern fight methodology. Screen-displaying helmets, capable of displaying maps and video from other group members, and types of physiological sensors to monitor health indicators. The devices can enhance wakefulness in accordance with the environment, not only for the soldier on the battlefield but also for all the members of the military at the base station and they can exchange data using wireless communication. But the primary issue was to design a light system, which could

achieve the desired outcome. One of the fundamental challenge in military missions is that the troopers are not able to connect with the base station. Moreover, precise navigation among the soldiers plays a valuable role in cautious forecasting. The defence wing of a nation should be efficient for the security of the nation, and soldiers too should be efficient.

The base unit acquires the location of a soldier with the help of GPS. The responsibility of base station operators is to help the soldiers choose the right path, if there is a threat of missing soldiers. The base unit will contact the standing of the soldier that is exhibited on the computer. Hence, they can yield instant action by directing assistance for the soldier requested by soldiers having a soldier unit. With the use of several biomedical sensors, the health constraints of soldiers are monitored, the location and placement of soldiers are confined by the use of a GPS module.

We aimed to introduce a cost-effective and dependable project that would assist the base unit, as much as the health and safety of the soldiers, during times of war, and special operations. Soldiers can also send secret messages to base stations for some kind of help that they want within a period.

Indian soldiers are mostly renowned for their courage, even without ammunition and protective measures; they have many triumphs to their name. Everyone should be concerned about the safety of the soldiers, so we have planned to build a project which will efficiently track the health status of the soldier, and his precise location to offer him necessary medical treatments as soon as possible.

Soldier tracking is performed with the help of GPS and ESP8266 is employed to give a wireless communication system. For monitoring the health parameters of soldiers we are employing biomedical sensors like temperature sensors and heartbeat sensors. An oxygen level sensor is employed to monitor atmospheric oxygen so if there are any Climatic changes the soldiers will be provided accordingly. So, this paper is all about tracking the location of soldiers from GPS, which is helpful for control room stations to know the exact location of soldiers and accordingly, will guide them it is for high-speed, short-range, soldier-to-soldier wireless Communications to relay information on situational Awareness with Bio-medical sensors, GPS navigation.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system is based on Arduino Uno, incorporating a GPS Neo-6M module for tracking, a GSM SIM900A for SMS-based communication, an LM35 temperature sensor, and an LDR sensor for heart rate monitoring. It also includes a 16×2 LCD with an I2C module for on-device visualization. While this system provides basic functionality, it has several drawbacks, including limited network coverage (GSM-dependent), lower accuracy in health monitoring, lack of environmental hazard detection, and no real-time IoT connectivity.

The Soldier Health and Position Tracking System is an advanced technology aimed at increasing the safety, efficiency, and well-being of soldiers by real-time tracking of health and geographical location. The systems employ a mix of wearable devices, GPS tracking, biometric sensors, and communication technology to track the physical health and location of soldiers in operational theatres. Health monitoring elements usually entail wearable sensors in the form of chest straps, wristbands, or smart clothes with biometric sensors that monitor vital signs including heart rate, body temperature, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and hydration level. The devices can identify fatigue, stress, or injury and send vital information to commanders and medical personnel, who can take swift action in the event of an emergency

For instance, wearable medical sensors can track the heart rate variability of a soldier to evaluate the level of fatigue or warn the command centre when a soldier's physiological measurements exceed safe boundaries, signalling potential medical conditions such as dehydration, heat stress, or cardiac distress. Apart from these medical monitors, injury-detection capabilities are also built into some systems. Impact sensors will identify shock waves resulting from concussions or trauma to the body, while more sophisticated systems will track patterns of movement in order to identify symptoms of injury

Where there is expected to be poor strength of GPS signals, e.g., in heavily populated areas or indoors, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), or mesh networks are employed in position tracking. These systems retain soldier location information through a network of devices connected to each other, with the ability for people to remain connected to their unit and headquarters even in blocked or remote areas. Real-Time Location Systems (RTLS) are also employed in military contexts for tracking soldiers' positions indoors or in complex environments, providing a better picture for commanders of the movement of troops. Sophisticated communication systems, such as tactical mesh networks, also ensure soldiers remain in contact with each other, providing health and position data even where there is no traditional communication infrastructure. Most current military tracking systems combine both position tracking and health monitoring in a single system, where sensor and GPS device data is sent to a central command centre. The data is displayed in real-time on dashboards, providing commanders with a full picture of the health status of their troops and movement. The system automatically issues alerts when a

soldier's health data is out of normal limits or when they deviate from their planned course, allowing swift action to be taken if necessary.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

To overcome the disadvantages of these limitations, our proposed system replaces the existing model with next-generation IoT technology and more accurate sensors. GSM-based SMS transmission is substituted with the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module for real-time monitoring using the Blynk app. The LM35 sensor is substituted with a DS18B20 digital temperature sensor, which gives more accurate readings. An LDR-based heart rate sensor is substituted with an MAX30100 pulse oximeter, which measures heart rate as well as oxygen saturation (SpO₂) with accuracy. For further increase soldier safety, a gas sensor (MQ-135) is used to sense harmful gases in the air. The entire system is based on Arduino Uno, which processes sensor data efficiently and wirelessly transmits it. The proposed Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System based on IoT monitors the health and position of soldiers in real-time using multiple sensors and communication modules. The GPS module identifies the geographical position of the soldier through the provision of latitude and longitude values.

The functioning of the Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System on the IoT starts with Arduino Uno, which gathers real-time data from all the sensors such as the MAX30100 pulse oximeter for heart rate and SpO₂ level, DS18B20 digital sensor for body temperature, and MQ-135 gas sensor for toxic gas detection in the atmosphere. The GPS Neo-6M module, simultaneously, monitors the location of the soldier continuously and sends latitude and longitude values. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module sends all the gathered data wirelessly to the Blynk IoT platform, enabling remote monitoring by a smartphone or computer. Whenever any parameter exceeds safe limits—such as abnormal heart rate, oxygen level, body temperature, or toxic gas detection—there is an immediate alert sent to the command centre to act immediately. In comparison to the conventional systems of SMS-based alert, this IoT-based real-time solution provides real-time monitoring, quicker emergency response, and improved battlefield situational awareness, and thus much-improved soldier safety and mission efficiency.

Fig 3.1 Proposed system Block Diagram

B. METHODOLOGY

Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System via IoT is based on a sequential approach, with sensor initialization and data reading using MAX30100 (heart rate & SpO₂ sensor), DS18B20 (body temperature sensor), MQ-135 (gas sensor), GPS Neo-6M (location tracking module), and an emergency alert push button, all connected with Arduino Uno. The system continually gathers health, environmental, and location information, which is subsequently processed to detect abnormal conditions. When heart rate, SpO₂, temperature, or gas levels reach dangerous levels, or when the panic button is activated, the system sends an alarm. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module sends real-time data to the Blynk cloud platform, and military personnel can track soldiers' health, environmental, and location information remotely. The system is in a closed loop, with 24/7 real-time monitoring, emergency response, and improved soldier safety in life-threatening situations.

C. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig 3.8 Circuit diagram

The Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System combines various sensors and modules with an Arduino Uno to track real-time health indicators, ambient conditions, and position. A regulated 5V and 3.3V power supply power the system to ensure the steady operation of all components. The MAX30100 pulse oximeter detects heart rate and SpO₂ via I2C communication, while the DS18B20 digital sensor tracks body temperature via the one-wire protocol. Also, the MQ-135 gas sensor is linked to Arduino's analog input (A0) to sense harmful gases. A push button (emergency alarm system) is connected to a digital input pin and sends an alarm when activated.

To implement location tracking, the GPS Neo-6M module is interfaced using UART (TX/RX interface) to display the real-time longitude and latitude coordinates. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module interfaced using TX/RX pins supports wireless transmission of data to the Blynk app to allow remote health monitoring and tracking of the soldier's location. The ESP8266 works on 3.3V; thus, the voltage divider circuit protects it from destruction by 5V signals. Data from every sensor is received and processed by the Arduino Uno before sending to the cloud of Blynk, through which soldiers are tracked remotely by the military personnel.

The whole circuit is built with continuous monitoring and real-time alarm capabilities. When any health parameter

goes beyond safety limits, if there are toxic gases present, or when the panic button is activated, an alarm is automatically triggered through ESP8266 to the Blynk app. The system ensures real-time GPS tracking, thus allowing the authorities to find and rescue soldiers in trouble. This fusion of IoT technology with security and health systems improves the efficiency and safety of military operations and thus becomes an important system for contemporary defense use.

D.FLOW CHART

IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXISTING SYSTEM AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

Component	Existing System	Proposed System
Microcontroller	Arduino Uno	Arduino Uno
Position Tracking	GPS Neo-6M	GPS Neo-6M
Communication Module	GSM SIM900A (SMS)	ESP8266 Wi-Fi (IoT-based real-time monitoring)
Temperature Sensor	LM35	DS18B20 (More accurate digital sensor)
Heart Rate Sensor	LDR Sensor	MAX30100 (Pulse oximeter for accurate heart rate & SpO ₂)
Gas Detection	Not available	Gas Sensor (e.g., MQ-135 for air quality monitoring)
Display	16x2 LCD (I2C)	Data displayed remotely via the Blynk App
Power Supply	Standard Battery	Can integrate rechargeable or solar options
Remote Monitoring	Limited to SMS notifications	Live data monitoring via cloud (Blynk app)
Energy Efficiency	Higher power consumption (GSM module)	Lower power consumption (Wi-Fi module is more efficient)

Table 4.1 Comparison Between Existing System and Proposed System

The given system effectively implements an integration of different sensors and communications modules in delivering real-time medical monitoring and global positioning tracking for soldiers. Outcomes-based on the system provide enhanced precision, quicker information relay, and effective remote control against conventional methodologies.

Throughout the test, the MAX30100 sensor delivered proper heart rate and SpO₂ values, which enabled constant tracking of the soldier's cardiovascular well-being. The DS18B20 temperature sensor showed exact body temperature values, providing real-time monitoring of possible fever or hypothermia conditions. The MQ-135 gas sensor efficiently measured the presence of toxic gases within the environment and issued warnings upon exceeding safe gas levels. The GPS Neo-6 module was able to deliver live location information and sent latitude and longitude coordinates with little error.

The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module facilitated effortless wireless communication with the Blynk IoT platform, where the military command centre could view soldiers' vitals and positions remotely. In contrast to the current system where GSM-based SMS notifications were used, the suggested system facilitated real-time data visualization, logging, and analysis via the Blynk app, enhancing response time and decision-making.

The push button emergency alert also worked well, directly notifying the command center on the instant activation, making it possible to respond quickly in situations of urgency. The power management system, such as the regulated voltage supply for ESP8266 and GPS modules, maintained stable and efficient operation under field conditions.

Overall, the results confirm that the proposed system is more reliable, efficient, and responsive, offering a comprehensive solution for soldier health and position tracking in military applications.

V.RESULT

A)

B)

Fig 5.1 Result

Component	Function	Performance Results	Remarks
MAX30100 (Heart Rate & SpO₂ Sensor)	Measures heart rate and oxygen saturation (SpO ₂)	Provided accurate and stable readings, but was affected by finger placement and motion artifacts	Highly reliable for continuous health monitoring
DS18B20 (Temperature Sensor)	Measures body temperature	Accurate ±0.5°C, stable readings in different environments	More precise than LM35, suitable for real-time health tracking
MQ-135 (Gas Sensor)	Detects toxic gases and air quality	Successfully detected harmful	Needs calibration for

		gases; required preheating for stable results.	optimal performance
GPS Neo-6M (Location Tracking Module)	Provides real-time GPS coordinates	2–3-meter accuracy, performed best in open areas, slightly affected in urban/forest areas	Good for tracking, but may need correction in signal-blocked areas
ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module	Enables IoT communication via Blynk	Fast and efficient data transmission, more power-efficient than GSM	Requires stable internet connection

Table 5.2 Performance of the components

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System based on IoT offers a complete and cost-effective solution for real-time monitoring of health, detection of environmental hazards, GPS tracking, and emergency notification. By combining MAX30100, DS18B20, MQ-135, GPS Neo-6M, and ESP8266 Wi-Fi modules, the system provides proper and uninterrupted observation of soldiers' vital parameters with easy data communication through IoT (Blynk platform). In comparison to existing GSM-based systems, the current system provides enhanced, quicker, more dependable, and energy-conscious communication, offering improved situational awareness and reaction time. Adding a push-button emergency alert mechanism further enhances the safety of the soldier by providing manual distress calling in extreme scenarios. With its capability of offering real-time remote monitoring and immediate alerts, this system dramatically improves military surveillance and decision-making, providing greater protection and effectiveness in combat and remote operations.

The future horizon of the Advanced Soldier Health and Position Tracking System based on IoT involves several improvements to enhance accuracy, efficiency, and real-time responsiveness. The use of AI and machine learning can facilitate predictive health monitoring, identifying anomalies in heart rate, oxygen saturation, and body temperature before critical conditions develop. Miniaturization and wearable

sensor development can increase the comfort and mobility of soldiers, thus making the system more conducive for use in the military. Advanced satellite-enabled GPS technologies like GLONASS or Galileo can enhance the accuracy of location, allowing accurate tracking even in sparsely populated or terrain-filled areas. Battery life extension using solar charging or energy harvesting can maximize operating time, making the system more operational in battlefield environments. Improving communication security with encrypted data transmission will keep confidential military data safe from cyber-attacks. The system can be integrated with military command centres to receive battlefield intelligence in real-time, enabling instantaneous decision-making. Voice command and AI-driven assistance can also enhance usability in battle, enabling hands-free control.

VII. REFERENCES

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